

**YORUBA RELIGIO-CULTURAL COSMOGONY:
REFLECTIONS ON EPISTEMOLOGICAL AND
CONTEMPORARY RELEVANCE**

By

OLUSANYA, Kayode John

Department of Religious Studies
Tai Solarin Federal University of Education,
Ijagun, Ogun State.
+2348053247066
olusanyakj@tasued.edu.ng

OYEBANJO, Olusegun Olatunji

Department Religious Studies,
Tai Solarin Federal University of Education,
Ijagun, Ogun State
+2348076173953
oyebanjoo@tasued.edu.ng

&

MICHEAL, Jacob Boluwatife

Department of Religious Studies
Tai Solarin Federal University of Education,
Ijagun Ogun State.
michealjb@tasued.edu.ng
+2347069264126

Abstract

This study explores Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony within the context of Africa Indigenous Religion (AIR) and evaluates its epistemic and contemporary relevance in view of claims regarding the origin of the universe in scientific cosmology. Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony provides a detailed account of the origin of the universe, the existence and creation of humans, moral and social order, and emphasizes the roles *Olódùmarè* and the *òrìṣà* in maintaining cosmic

order and harmony. In contrast, scientific cosmology relies on empirical observation, theoretical physics and mathematical modeling to explain the origin of the universe and evolution of life, including Big Bang theory and cosmic expansion. The study adopted a qualitative research methodology, employing literary analysis of primary and secondary sources, including the Yoruba oral traditions, *Ifá* corpus and scholarly works on African religion and scientific cosmology as well as comparative analysis. Findings reveal that each account has its own distinct strengths and limitations. Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony provides meaning to existence, creation, destiny, ethical guidance, while scientific cosmology provides reliable evidence-based explanations of physical processes. The study concluded that Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony offers cultural, ethical, and philosophical resources that complements rather than conflict with scientific knowledge. The study therefore recommended the integration of Yoruba indigenous knowledge into education curriculum for the purpose of promoting interdisciplinary engagements to foster dialogue between scientific and traditional perspectives. This underscores the continued relevance of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony in the contemporary society.

Keywords: Yoruba, cosmogony, scientific cosmology, epistemology, relevance.

Introduction

Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony is endowed with rich account of the origin and order of the universe as understood within Yoruba indigenous religion. The ideas about the creation and origin of the universe among Yoruba people of Southwest Nigeria, are preserved through oral traditions, especially by *Ifá* corpus, myths, ritual practices and sacred poetry. These oral sources explain the relationship between the Supreme Being known as *Olódùmarè*, the divinities (*òrìṣà*), and humans, in maintaining the order and harmony of the universe. Scholars have long observed that this creation account function as vehicles for transmitting knowledge about creation, existence, destiny and structure of reality (Idowu, 1962).

The universe is understood in Yoruba belief as an interaction between the spiritual and physical realms. The creation traditions often recount how the divinities were sent by *Olódùmarè* to shape and cultivate the earth for human habitation. Such

account emphasized purpose, order and dependence of human life on divine authority. Idowu (1962) in *Olódùmarè: God in Yoruba belief*, affirmed the divine transcendence of God while also recognizing the active roles of divinity in maintaining social order and harmony of the universe.

The study of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony has attracted attention because of its religious significance and philosophical questions raised about knowledge and reality. Africa traditions have gained momentum as important source for intellectual knowledge rather than merely cultural artifacts. Scholars are of the view that Africa indigenous religion contributes to global discussions on metaphysics, ethics and the meaning of existence (Olupona, 2014). Within this purview, the idea of Yoruba cosmology began to shape identity, culture and religious practises among indigenous people in Africa and the diaspora.

In similar vein, modern scientific cosmological theories provide explanation of the origin of the universe through observation, experiment and theoretical physics, especially through Big Bang Theory and other scientific theory. The encounter between scientific explanation of the origin of the universe and the traditional account presents careful reflections on their assumptions and purposes. The scientific cosmology seems to offer measurable explanation of cosmic origin while Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony addresses questions of meaning, human purpose, and moral order.

An examination of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony and scientific cosmology provides an opportunity to access the continual relevance of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony in contemporary scholarship. Such inquiry is capable of fostering knowledge and clarifies how Yoruba indigenous knowledge traditions contribute to discussions about philosophy, culture, and religion. By examining these themes, this study seeks to clarify the significance of Yoruba indigenous religion as a source of knowledge in the humans search for meaning and purpose of life.

This study therefore examines Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony as both a cultural narrative and an epistemological insight, exploring its contemporary relevance in a world increasingly shaped by scientific rationality and globalization. By situating Yoruba cosmological thought alongside scientific

accounts of the universe, the study seeks to assess its enduring significance, intellectual contributions, and limitations, while also considering the broader implications for the preservation and reinterpretation of indigenous knowledge systems in modern scholarship.

Overview of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony

The origin of the universe, formation of the earth, and the place of humanity within a divinely created order are explained in Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony. In Yoruba indigenous religion, creation traditions are preserved mainly through oral tradition, *Ifá* literary corpus, myths, and rituals. These sources are essential in understanding how the world came into existence and how spiritual forces continue to influence human existence. Rather than presenting creation as a purely physical event, Yoruba thoughts connect cosmology with moral order, destiny and communal responsibility (Abimbola, 1977).

A major idea in the Yoruba creation account is the belief in a supreme being known as *Olódùmarè*, who is regarded as the ultimate source of life and authority. Yoruba indigenous religion sees Olodumare as transcendent yet actively involved in the maintenance and sustenance of the universe through his divinities known as *òrìṣà*, who oversee the active day-to-day activities of the universe. In Yoruba belief, *Olódùmarè* delegate cosmic administration to the divinities, who serve as intermediaries between heaven and earth (Bascom, 1969). This is understood as a hierarchy order in which divine power flows from *Olódùmarè* to the *òrìṣà* and ultimately to humans.

It is believed in the Yoruba creation account that the earth was originally covered by primordial waters. *Olódùmarè* then commissioned a divine being known as Obatala or Odùduwà depending on the versions, to descend from heaven with the sacred materials to form a dry land. These materials include sand, a hen to spread the sand, and a palm nut symbolizing life and growth. The land emerged at Ilé-Ifè through this act, which is regarded as a spiritual center of creation in Yoruba traditions. These traditions did not only explain the origin of physical world, but also establishes Ilé-Ifè as a sacred place of historical and spiritual significance (Olupona, 2014).

The creation of human being is another important element of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony. In several accounts, Ọbatala is entrusted with the work of moulding the human body from the clay, while *Olódùmarè* breathed life into the formed body. This account emphasized the belief that humans possess physical and spiritual dimensions. It further explains the Yoruba understanding of destiny (*Ayanmo/orí*), which one chose before birth, and this shapes an individual's life path. Through this belief, cosmology becomes closely linked with ethics, since individuals are expected to live in harmony with divine order and communal values (Abimbola, 1977).

The Yoruba view the universe as two interconnected realms; visible world (*ayé*) and the spiritual realm (*òrun*). These realms interact continuously through rituals and religious observances. The *Ifá* system of divination plays crucial roles in maintaining the balance between these realms by providing guidance and instructions from the spiritual world (Morton-Williams, 1964). In the general African indigenous religion perspectives, Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony is not limited to explain the origin of the universe alone, but it also extends to address ongoing relationship between humans, divinities and ancestors (Olupona, 2014).

The universe according to Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony is seen as orderly and purposeful, governed by moral principles and instructions that encourage good character (*ìwà*). Harmony in the society is believed to reflect harmony in the cosmos, while evil and wrongdoing disrupt spiritual the social balance in the universe. This ethical dimension demonstrates that cosmological beliefs are closely tied to social norms, law and cultural identity within Yoruba communities (Awolalu & Dopamu, 1979).

Yoruba cosmological ideas should not be viewed as mere myths but expressions of philosophical reflection on meaning, existence and human purpose. In this context, it provides explanations for destiny, suffering, and the nature of divine authority why reinforcing communal cohesion. In this view, Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony serves as a religious narrative and a source of knowledge about reality which continues to influence cultural and religious life (Olupona, 2014). Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony offers a comprehensive understanding of the universe in relation to creation, morality, human destiny. This holistic view

remains central to Yoruba indigenous religion and continues to shape religious practice, cultural identity, and philosophical reflection among the Yoruba people and in the African diaspora.

Description of Scientific Cosmology

Scientific cosmology is a branch of astrophysics that study the origin, evolution, structure, and large-scale of the universe. Scientific cosmology is the outcome of systematic observation, mathematical calculations, and testable hypotheses unlike mythological or purely philosophical account of cosmic origins. The development of scientific cosmology has been shaped by advances physics, astronomy, and space science over the past century (Planck Collaboration, 2020). The Big Bang Theory is a foundation of modern cosmology which proposes that the universe came into existence approximately 13.8 billion years ago from an extremely hot and dense state and has been expanding ever since (Planck Collaboration, 2020). The evidence of expansion was first reported by Edwin Hubble, who demonstrated that galaxies have been receding from the Earth at a velocity proportional to their distance (Hubble, 1929). The discovery affirmed strong empirical support for early theories proposed by George Lemaitre, who was of the opinion that the universe originated from a primeval atom (Lemaitre, 1931). Another affirmation of the Big Bang Theory came with the detection of cosmic microwave background radiation by Arno Penzias and Robert Wilson in 1965. The radiation is interpreted as residual thermal energy from the early universe and is considered one of the strongest pieces of evidence for the Big Bang Theory (Planck Collaboration, 2020).

Modern scientific theory that supports cosmology theory was derived from general theory of relativity, developed by Albert Einstein in 1916, which describe gravity as the curvature of space time caused by mass and energy, which enable scientists to model cosmic expansion, and the large-scale structure of the universe (Ryden, 2017). Modern cosmology also examines the composition of the universe. Observation of galaxy rotation curves and gravitational lens which suggests that the presence of dark matter and measurement of distance, which indicate that the expansion of the universe is accelerating due to what is termed dark energy (Riess et al.) It has been explained that although, these components

are not directly observable, their effects are measurable and form an essential part of current cosmological theory (Abbott et al., 2026).

The major strength of scientific cosmology lies in its methodological commitment to empirical verification and continuous refinement. Cosmological theories are not treated as one-time-fits-all knowledge or dogma. Rather, they are tested against observation and data are obtained through ground-based telescopes, space satellite, and particle physics experiments. The ongoing process of hypothesis testing and data analysis ensure that cosmology remain a dynamic and self-correcting field of inquiry (Ryden, 2017).

Respective Strengths and Limitations of Each Account

A comparative examination of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony and scientific cosmology reveals that both offer valuable insights into the origin and nature of the universe; though they differ significantly in purpose, method, and scope. Each account possesses particular strengths that make it meaningful within its own context, while also presenting certain limitations when evaluated from alternative perspectives.

Strengths of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony

A major strength of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony lies in its holistic understanding of reality. Within Yoruba indigenous religion, explanations of the universe are closely linked with moral values, social order, and human purpose. Creation narratives do not merely describe how the world began but also explain how humans should live within it. This integration of cosmology with ethics encourages communal responsibility and the cultivation of good character (*iwà*), which remains central to Yoruba cultural life (Awolalu & Dopamu, 1979).

In addition to the above is its capacity to provide meaning and existential orientation. By presenting the universe as purposeful and divinely ordered under *Olódùmarè*, Yoruba cosmology addresses questions about destiny, suffering, and human identity. Accordingly, the cosmological vision of the Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony affirms divine sovereignty while emphasizing the interconnectedness of spiritual and physical realities (Idowu, 1962). This perspective offers psychological and spiritual reassurance that scientific explanations often do not attempt to provide.

Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony also preserves cultural identity and historical continuity. Through oral traditions and ritual practices, cosmological narratives serve as repositories of collective memory and indigenous knowledge. Scholars note that such traditions contribute to philosophical reflection by offering alternative ways of understanding existence beyond purely material explanations (Olupona, 2014).

Limitations of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony

Despite its cultural and spiritual significance, Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony faces limitations when assessed using scientific criteria. Its reliance on oral tradition and symbolic narratives means that its claims are not empirically verifiable. As a result, it does not provide measurable explanations of physical processes such as cosmic expansion or the formation of galaxies. This makes it less applicable in scientific investigations of the natural world (Abimbola, 1977), which is no doubt an ennobling task.

Another limitation is that variations in oral accounts may lead to multiple interpretations of creation narratives. While such diversity reflects the richness of the tradition, it can make systematic analysis difficult, especially in academic contexts that prioritize uniformity and precise documentation.

Strengths of Scientific Cosmology

Scientific cosmology's greatest strength lies in its empirical foundation. Through observation, experimentation, and mathematical modeling, it provides detailed explanations of cosmic phenomena such as the origin of the universe, the formation of stars, and the large-scale structure of space. The predictive power of scientific theories allows for continuous testing and refinement, contributing to technological and intellectual advancement (Ryden, 2017).

Another indication of strength is its universality. Scientific explanations are not tied to a particular culture or religious tradition, making them widely applicable across different societies. In summation of a brief history of time, scientific inquiry seeks general laws that apply throughout the universe, thereby offering a shared framework for understanding cosmic history (Hawking, 1988).

Scientific cosmology also encourages critical thinking and openness to revision. The willingness to modify theories in light of new evidence ensures that knowledge continues to develop, making science a dynamic and progressive enterprise (Weinberg, 1993).

Limitations of Scientific Cosmology

In spite of its attraction, scientific cosmology has limitations, particularly in addressing questions of meaning, purpose, and moral order. While it explains how the universe developed, it does not provide answers to existential questions about why the universe exists or what constitutes a good life. These important concerns fall outside the scope of empirical investigation and are often addressed by religious traditions (Olupona, 2014).

Another limitation is that certain aspects of the universe, such as dark matter and dark energy, remain poorly understood, indicating that scientific knowledge is provisional and still incomplete. Moreover, the highly technical nature of cosmological theories can make them inaccessible to non-specialists, limiting their broader cultural impact compared to traditional narratives.

Comparative Reflection

When considered together, Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony and scientific cosmology can be seen as addressing different dimensions of human inquiry (Segla, 2016). Yoruba cosmology provides moral and spiritual interpretation, while scientific cosmology offers physical and empirical explanation. Rather than viewing one as replacing the other, many scholars suggest that they can be appreciated as complementary approaches that respond to different human needs and questions (Hawking, 1988). Each account demonstrates unique strengths shaped by its goals and methods, as well as limitations that arise when evaluated outside its intended scope. Understanding these differences allows for a more balanced appreciation of both indigenous knowledge traditions and scientific inquiry in the study of the universe.

Arguments for Retention or Rejection of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony

Debates about whether Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony should be retained or rejected often arise within broader discussions about modernization, scientific

advancement, and the place of indigenous knowledge in contemporary society (Mogaji, 2025). While some argue that traditional cosmologies should give way to scientific explanations, others maintain that they remain valuable as sources of cultural identity, moral guidance, and philosophical insight (Catalani, 2025). Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony, in particular, offers enduring ethical frameworks through concepts like *ìwà* (good character) and harmony with the cosmos, which continue to foster communal cohesion and personal responsibility even amid rapid technological change (Oyinlade, 2024). Moreover, elements of Yoruba cosmology such as *Ifá* divination and generative systems have been interpreted by scholars as displaying proto-scientific logic, binary reasoning, and systemic thinking that parallel aspects of modern mathematics, complexity science, and even quantum-informed views, suggesting potential compatibility rather than inherent conflict. (Segla, 2016).

A balanced assessment, in the opinion of Olupona (2014) is the suggestion that the question is not simply one of acceptance or dismissal but of understanding the distinct roles that Yoruba cosmology continues to play. Retention is advocated not as opposition to science but as a complementary epistemology that addresses existential, moral, and relational dimensions of human experience which empirical science alone may not fully encompass, thereby supporting cultural resilience in the face of globalization and decolonial efforts (Catalani, 2025).

Arguments for Retention

One strong argument for retaining Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony is its cultural significance. Within Yoruba indigenous religion, cosmological narratives form part of the historical memory and identity of the Yoruba people. They preserve collective values, explain social institutions, and reinforce a sense of continuity between past and present. Scholars emphasize that indigenous cosmologies serve as important expressions of how societies interpret their world and transmit knowledge across generations (Awolalu & Dopamu, 1979). Rejecting such traditions entirely would risk eroding cultural heritage and weakening communal identity.

Another argument for retention is its ethical relevance. Yoruba cosmology links the origin of the universe with moral order, emphasizing the importance of good

character (*ìwà*), responsibility, and harmony within society. Idowu (1962), for instance, argued that the belief in a divinely ordered universe under *Olódùmarè* encourages moral living and social accountability (Idowu, 1962). In this sense, Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony continues to offer ethical insights that remain meaningful even in modern contexts where moral challenges persist.

Retention is also supported by the growing recognition of indigenous knowledge systems within global scholarship. Scholars such as Olupona argue that African religious traditions provide valuable perspectives on spirituality, ecology, and community life that complement scientific knowledge rather than compete with it (Olupona, 2014). Yoruba cosmology, therefore, contributes to intellectual diversity by offering alternative ways of interpreting existence and human purpose.

Furthermore, Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony addresses existential questions that scientific cosmology does not attempt to answer, such as the meaning of life, destiny, and the relationship between humanity and the divine. Its symbolic narratives provide psychological comfort and spiritual orientation, particularly within religious communities where these beliefs remain central to daily life.

Arguments for Rejection

Despite its significance, some scholars argue that Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony should not be treated as a literal explanation of the physical origin of the universe. From a scientific standpoint, its narratives are based on symbolic and mythic traditions rather than empirical observation. As a result, they do not provide verifiable explanations of cosmic processes such as the expansion of the universe or the formation of galaxies (Ryden, 2017).

Another argument for rejection is that strict adherence to traditional cosmological interpretations may discourage critical inquiry if they are presented as unquestionable truths. In educational contexts, reliance solely on traditional explanations without engagement with scientific perspectives could limit students' understanding of modern scientific developments. This concern has led some scholars to advocate for a reinterpretation rather than outright acceptance of traditional cosmological claims (Abimbola, 1977).

The diversity of creation narratives within Yoruba oral tradition can make it difficult to establish a single authoritative account. While this diversity reflects the richness of the tradition, critics argue that it complicates attempts to present Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony as a systematic explanation comparable to scientific theories.

Towards a Balanced Position

Rather than choosing between complete retention or total rejection, some scholars support a middle position that recognizes Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony as a symbolic and philosophical account rather than a scientific one. From this perspective, Yoruba cosmology should be retained for its cultural, religious, and ethical contributions while scientific cosmology should be used for explaining physical processes. This approach allows both knowledge systems to coexist without forcing one to replace the other.

Such a position acknowledges that Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony addresses questions of meaning, value, and human purpose, while science focuses on measurable aspects of the universe. Recognizing these distinct roles encourages dialogue between tradition and modern knowledge rather than conflict. As noted by some scholars of African religion, indigenous cosmologies remain relevant when interpreted within their proper cultural and philosophical contexts (Olupona, 2014).

The question of retaining or rejecting Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony should not be framed as a simple choice between tradition and modernity. While it may not serve as a scientific explanation of cosmic origins, it remains valuable as a source of cultural identity, ethical teaching, and spiritual reflection. A critical yet appreciative approach that preserves its symbolic and philosophical insights while engaging scientific knowledge offers the most balanced way forward.

Summary

This study has examined Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony as an account of the origin and order of the universe within Yoruba indigenous religion and has considered its relevance in view of advances in scientific cosmology. The discussion began by explaining how Yoruba creation traditions present the universe as a divinely ordered reality shaped by *Olódùmarè* and sustained through

the activities of the *òrìṣà*. These traditions, preserved through oral literature and religious practice, show that cosmological ideas among the Yoruba are closely connected with moral values, social relationships, and human destiny.

The study also explored the main features of scientific cosmology, noting its reliance on observation, mathematical reasoning, and theoretical models such as the Big Bang theory. Scientific cosmology provides detailed explanations of physical processes and has significantly expanded knowledge about the structure and evolution of the universe. However, its primary concern remains the description of natural phenomena rather than questions of meaning or moral purpose.

A comparative analysis of both accounts showed that Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony and scientific cosmology address different dimensions of human inquiry. Yoruba cosmology offers insights into ethical living, spiritual relationships, and the search for meaning, while scientific cosmology provides empirically grounded explanations of cosmic development. Each account therefore possesses strengths shaped by its aims, as well as limitations when judged outside its intended scope.

The discussion on whether Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony should be retained or rejected highlighted the importance of cultural continuity and intellectual diversity. While it may not function as a scientific explanation of the physical universe, Yoruba cosmology remains significant as a source of philosophical reflection, moral teaching, and cultural identity. Scholars of African religion have emphasized that indigenous cosmologies should be understood within their cultural contexts rather than dismissed because they differ from scientific explanations (Mbiti, 1969).

Conclusion

Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony remains a religious and cultural expression of how Yoruba people understand existence, destiny, and the relationship between the physical and spiritual realm. Its narratives provide meaning to reality, ethical orientation that remains valuable in contemporary Society. At the same time, scientific cosmology provides a reliable and verified explanation of physical reality to empirical investigation and theoretical analysis.

Rather than seeing the two account of the origin of universe as competing explanations, it is essential to integrate complementary perspectives to allow each account to be appreciated for its unique contribution. Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony attempts to understand human values and spiritual life, while scientific cosmology advanced knowledge of the natural world. It is essential to recognize the distinct rules of both traditions to encourage a more inclusive approach to knowledge direct cultural heritage while embracing scientific discovery.

Recommendations

Based on the discussion of Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony and scientific cosmology, some recommendations can be made to encourage a balanced appreciation of indigenous knowledge and scientific inquiry.

- i. There is a need to promote the academic study of Yoruba indigenous religion within schools and universities. Including Yoruba cosmological ideas in religious studies, philosophy, and cultural studies curricula will help preserve indigenous knowledge and deepen students' understanding of African intellectual traditions. Scholars have long emphasized that African religious thought provides important insights into morality, community life, and human existence (Mbiti, 1969). Such inclusion will also help correct the historical marginalization of indigenous perspectives in formal education.
- ii. Yoruba religio-cultural cosmogony should be interpreted symbolically and philosophically rather than as a literal scientific account of cosmic origins. This approach would allow its teachings on morality, destiny, and social harmony to remain relevant while avoiding unnecessary conflict with scientific explanations. Interpreting traditional narratives in this way encourages dialogue between religion and science rather than opposition.
- iii. Further interdisciplinary research should be encouraged. Scholars in religious studies, anthropology, philosophy, and the natural sciences should collaborate to explore how indigenous cosmologies contribute to contemporary discussions on ethics, ecology, and human identity. Such research will highlight the continuing relevance of Yoruba cosmology in addressing modern social and environmental challenges.

- iv. Efforts should be made to preserve oral traditions and *Ifá* literature through documentation, translation, and digital archiving. Since much of Yoruba cosmological knowledge is transmitted orally, preservation initiatives are essential to prevent the loss of valuable cultural heritage. Supporting traditional custodians of knowledge, such as priests and oral historians, will also ensure continuity across generations.
- v. Public education should emphasize respect for cultural diversity in ways of understanding the universe. Encouraging mutual respect between scientific and indigenous perspectives will foster intellectual openness and cultural tolerance in pluralistic societies. This is especially important in contemporary Africa, where modernization often coexists with strong traditional beliefs.
- vi. Policymakers and cultural institutions should support programs that promote indigenous knowledge systems as part of national heritage. Recognizing Yoruba cosmology as an important cultural resource can strengthen identity, promote cultural pride, and contribute to broader discussions about knowledge production in Africa. As noted in *African Religions and Philosophy*, African religious traditions remain vital sources of wisdom and social values that continue to shape communities (Mbiti, 1969).

References

- Abbott, T. M. C., et al. (2026). Dark Energy Survey Year 6 results: Cosmological constraints from galaxy clustering and weak lensing. *arXiv*. <https://arxiv.org/abs/2601.14559>
- Abimbola, W. (1977). *Ifá: An exposition of Ifá literary corpus*. Oxford University Press.
- Awolalu, J. O., & Dopamu, P. A. (1979). *West African traditional religion*. Onibonoje Press & Book Industries.
- Bascom, W. (1969). *The Yoruba of southwestern Nigeria*. Holt, Rinehart and Winston.

- Catalani, A. (2025). We remember through the spirit: Yoruba intangible heritage, diasporic belonging, and the cultural work of Aladura Churches in the UK. *International Journal of Heritage Studies*. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21619441.2025.2590275>
- Einstein, A. (1916). The foundation of the general theory of relativity. *Annalen der Physik*, 49(7), 769–822.
- Hawking, S. (1988). *A brief history of time: From the big bang to black holes*. Bantam Books.
- Hubble, E. (1929). A relation between distance and radial velocity among extragalactic nebulae. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 15(3), 168–173.
- Idowu, E. B. (1962). *Olódùmarè: God in Yoruba belief*. Longman.
- Lemaître, G. (1931). The beginning of the world from the point of view of quantum theory. *Nature*, 127(3210), 706–707.
- Mbiti, J. S. (1969). *African religions and philosophy*. Heinemann.
- Mogaji, R. I. (2025). Assessing the Yoruba conservation approach in addressing contemporary environmental crises. *Crowther Journal of Arts and Humanities*, 2(4), 119–132. <https://acjol.org/index.php/crowther/article/view/6792>
- Morton-Williams, P. (1964). An outline of the cosmology and cult organization of the Oyo Yoruba. *Africa*, 34(3), 243–261.
- Olupona, J. K. (2014). *African religions: A very short introduction*. Oxford University Press.
- Oyinlade, E. O. (2024). Technological culture and the challenge of erosion of Yorùbá moral values. *African Journal of Culture, History and Religious Thought*, 7(3), 1–9. <https://abjournals.org/ajchrt/papers/volume-7/issue-3/technological-culture-and-the-challenge-of-erosion-of-yoruba-moral-values>
- Penzias, A. A., & Wilson, R. W. (1965). A measurement of excess antenna temperature at 4080 Mc/s. *Astrophysical Journal*, 142, 419–421.

- Planck Collaboration. (2020). Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 641, A6. <https://doi.org/10.1051/0004-6361/201833910>
- Riess, A. G., Filippenko, A. V., Challis, P., Clocchiatti, A., Diercks, A., Garnavich, P. M., Gilliland, R. L., Hogan, C. J., Jha, S., Kirshner, R. P., Leibundgut, B., Phillips, M. M., Prieto, J. L., Reiss, D. J., Schmidt, B.
- Schommer, R. A., Smith, R. C., Spyromilio, J., Stubbs, C., ... Suntzeff, N. B. (1998). Observational evidence from supernovae for an accelerating universe and a cosmological constant. *The Astronomical Journal*, 116(3), 1009–1038. <https://doi.org/10.1086/300499>
- Ryden, B. (2017). *Introduction to cosmology* (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Segla, D. A. (2016). Viewing formal mathematics from Yoruba conception of the sky. *Journal of Astronomy in Culture*, 1(1), 9–21. <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/4sk1p169>
- Weinberg, S. (1993). *The first three minutes: A modern view of the origin of the universe*. Basic Books.